

COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH TOWARDS RAKTPACHAK YOGA AND ITS
IMPLEMENTATION IN KUSHTHA AND KRIMIDr. Shubhda Rajesh Hadadare^{*1}, Dr. Prasanna Gavali²^{*1}PG Student, Dravyaguna Vigyan Department, LRP Medical College and Hospital, Islampur.²MD Dravyaguna, Professor Dravyaguna Department, Research Guide.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Shubhda Rajesh Hadadare**

PG Student, Dravyaguna Vigyan Department, LRP Medical College and Hospital, Islampur.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19327242>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Shubhda Rajesh Hadadare^{*1}, Dr. Prasanna Gavali². (2026). Computational Approach Towards Raktapachak Yoga And Its Implementation In Kushtha and Krimi. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(4), 250–254.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 03/03/2026

Article Revised on 23/03/2026

Article Published on 01/04/2026

ABSTRACT

Raktadhatupachak from vishamjwar chikitsa^[1] mentioned in charak chikitsa sthan contains drugs that shows krimighna karma. This includes patol, sariva, musta, patha, katuki. Various reference from different nighantus define krimighna as well as kushthaghna properties of these drugs. Certain types of krimi^[2] are elaborated in samhitas. Among these types raktaj krimi^[3] are responsible for kushtha vyadhi. Raktadhatupachak name itself defines gamitwa of these drugs into rakta dhatu. Such a contained combination can be implemented in raktaj krimi. Rakta dhatu pachak is not only limited to be used in raktadhatugat jwar. This expansion is explained on the basis of references collected from nighantus. Details about rasa veerya vipaka of drugs are mentioned in nighantus. Bruhatrayi have limited elaboration. Later in nighantukala Dravyaguna shastra took revamp and classification of dravya, types of dravya, their properties, synonyms were explained thoroughly in samhitas. Dosh, dushya, adhishthan are categorised and according to that physicians use these dhatupachak in different forms such as choorna, vati, kwath to treat various diseases.

KEYWORDS: Raktadhatupachak, raktaj krimi, kushtha, vishamjwar chikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda believes principal of cutting roots of vyadhi gives ultimate results (moole kuthare) Dosh samyata defines swasthya whereas dosha vaishamyaya causes vyadhi. When doshas are vitiated they impair dushyas i. e. Dhatu. This manifest various sign and symptoms and seen as vyadhi.

Hence to acquire dosha equilibrium one has to attain dhatu samyata. Doshas association with dushya is a origin of vyadhi. Agnimandya is fundamental cause of vyadhi. Jatharagni mandya further leads dhatwagni mandya. Rakta dhatugat doshas leads rakta dhatwagni mandya. It causes abhishyandan and provides adhishthan for krimi.

Raktaj krimi has specific characteristics which causes kushtha vyadhi. Rakta pitta ashrayashrayi^[6] sambandha leads rakta dushti. Dravyas included in Raktadhatupachak are primarily tikta rasa pradhan,

krimighna, kushthaghna^[7] and pittashamak properties.

This review on nighantus flashes conjoined concept of raktadhatupachak, krimi and kushtha. Jwar also known as amay vyadhi. Hence jwaraghna chikitsa can also be used as per Yukti praman in other vyadhi.

Kushtha vyadhi causes explained as sapta dravyani^[8] in charak samhita. Properties of sapta dravyani and raktadhatupachak are opposite to each other. Hence as per samanya vishesh siddhant^[9] this combination works against kushtha vyadhi.

Sira and kandara^[10] are known as updhatu of rakta dhatu. Therefore dushti of raktadhatu causes defects in sira and kandara. Particular type of raktaj krimi affect sira and kandara. Samanya krimi chikitsa^[11] upkram followed by Apakarshan, prakriti vighat, nidan parivarjan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samhita: Charak samhita, Sushrut samhita, Ashtang hriday

Nighantus: Bhavprakash nighantu, dhanvantari nighantu, kaiyyadev nighantu, Journal-Pubmed,

DHARA, Journal of ayurveda and integrated medical science (JAIMS) Journal of research in ayurvedic science (JRAS)

OBSERVATION**Review of Raktapachak yoga from Samhita and Nighantus****Bhavprakash**

पटोलं सारिवा मुस्ता पाठा कटुकिोहिणी

	Drug	Rasa	Veerya	Vipak
1.	Patol	Tikta, katu	Ushna	Katu
2.	Sariva	Madhur, tikta	Sheeta	Madhur
3.	Musta	Tikta, katu	Sheeta	Katu
4.	Patha	Tikta	Ushna	Katu
5.	Kutaki	Tikta	Sheeta	Katu

Patol

पटोलं पाचनं हृद्यं वृष्यं लघु अग्रनदीपन । म्लानधोष्ण िगत कासास्र ज्विदोषत्रय क्रिमि^[12] Pachan- Transformation of aama

Hridyam- Protects and nourishes cardiovascular system
Vrushya- Replenishes reproductive system
Agnideepan- Pacifies jatharagni-dhatwagni
Gunas- Snigdha, ushna
Rogaghnata- kasa, jwar(tridoshaj),raktaj vyadhi, krimi vikara

Sariva

सारिवा युगुलं स्वादु म्लानधं शुक्रकिं गुरू। अग्रनमातद्य अरूचच श्वास कासामववषनाशन॥ दोषत्रयास प्रदि ज्वािततसािनाशनम्^[13]

Rasa- madhur

Guna- Snigdha, guru

Shukrakara- Shukradhatu poshak

Rogaghnata- Agnimandya, aruchi, shwas- kasa, aamvish nashak, tridoshaj raktapradar, jwar, atisaar

Musta

मुस्तकं कटुकं हिमं ग्राहि ततक्तं दीपनपाचनम् । कषायं कफ वपत्तास्रं तृडज्विरुचचजन्तुहत्^[14] *Rasa- Katu, tikta, kashay*

Guna- Sheeta

Karma- Grahi- reabsorption of fluids in small intestine

Deepana -Pacifies jatharagni-dhatwagni
Pachan - Transformation of ama

Doshaghnata- Kapha, pitta, rakta

Rogaghnata- Trishna, jwar, aruchi, kasa, krimi vikara

Patha

पाठोष्णा कटुका तीक्ष्णा वातश्लेष्मििी लघु शूलज्विच्छदीकुष्ठाततसािहद्रुजः

दािकण्डूववषश्वासक्रिमिगुल्मगिग्रान्^[15] *Rasa- Katu*

Veerya – ushna

Vipak- katu

Guna- teekshna, laghu
Doshaghnata- vaat, kapha

Rogaghnata- Jwar, chardi, kushtha, atisaar, hrudruja, daah, kandu, visha, shwas, krimi vikara, gulma, garadosha, vrana dosh.

Kutaki

कटुकी तु कटुका पाके स्वादु ततक्ता रूक्षा हिमा लघुः । भेदनी दीपनी हृद्या कफवपत्तज्वािपा । प्रमेिश्वासकासास्र दािकुष्ठ कृममप्रणुत्।^[16]

Rasa- Tikta, madhur

Vipak- katu
Veerya – Sheeta

Guna- Rooksha, sheeta, laghu
Karma-

Bhedan – disruption of bandh aavran
Deepan- Transformation of aama

Hridyam- Protects and nourishes cardiovascular system

Doshaghnata- Kapha, pitta

Rogaghnata- Jwar, prameha, shwas- kasa, raktaj vyadhi, daah kushtha, krimi vikara.

Dhanwantari Nighantu**Patol**

Trichosanthes dioica Roxb. Fam. Cucurbitaceae.

षटोलः कुलकः प्रोक्तः पाण्डुकः ककशश्छदः ॥ ४८ ॥

िाजीफलः पाण्डुफलो िाजनामाऽमृताफलः । वीयशगभशप्रतानश्च कुष्ठा कासमुक्तदः ॥ ४६ ॥ पटोलं कटुकं ततक्तमुष्णं वपत्तवविचथ च । कफासूक्कण्डुकुष्ठानि ज्विदािौ च नाशयेत् ॥^[17] ५० ॥

Sariva

सारिवे द्वे तु मधुिे कफवातास्त्रनाशने ।

कृष्णमूली तु संप्राहिमशमशा कफवातगजत् ॥ १६० ॥

कुष्ठकण्डूनवििििे मेिदुगशग्धनाशने तृष्णा रुचचप्रशमनी िक्तवपत्तििा स्मृता ॥१६१॥^[18]

Musta

Cyperus rotundus Linn., *C. Scariosus* R. Br. Fam.-Cyperaceae.

मुस्ता चाम्बुधि मेघो घनो िाजकसेरुकः । भद्रमुस्तो विािोऽब्दो गाङ्गेयः कुरुवतदकः ॥ ३६ ॥ जीमूतोऽथ वृषध्वाङ्गी जलदोऽथ बलािकः ।

नादेयः वपण्डमुस्तोऽतयो नागिः परिकीवत्तशतः ॥ ४० ॥

मुस्ता ततक्तकषायाऽततमशमशा श्लेष्मिक्तगजत् । वपत्तज्वाितसािघ्नी दृष्णाकृमिववनामश ॥४१॥^[19]

Patha

Cissampelos pareira Linn.

Fam.-Menispermaceae.

पाठाऽम्बष्ठाऽम्बष्ठी च प्राचीना पापचेमलका । विततक्ता
बृविक्तक्ता पाहठका स्थापनी वृकी ॥ ६६ ॥ मालती च वि
देवी त्रत्रवृताऽतया शुभा मता ।

पाठा ततक्तिसा वृष्या ववषष्ठी कुष्ठकण्डुनुत् ॥ ७० ॥
छहदशहृद्रोगज्विजत् त्रत्रदोषशमनी पि । पाठाऽततसाऽिशूलघ्नी
कफवपत्तज्जिवापि ॥ ७१ ॥^[20]

Kutaki

Picrorhiza kurroa Royle ex Benth. Fam.-Scrophulariaceae.

कटुका मत्स्यशकला मत्स्यवपत्ता च िोहिणी । कृष्णभेदा
काण्डरुिा नाम्ना कटुकिोहिणी ॥ ३६ ॥ अशोकिोहिणी
ततक्ता चक्राङ्गी शकुलादनी । कटुिोहिण्यरिष्टा च प्रोक्ता
ततक्तकिोहिणी ॥ ३७ ॥ आमघ्नी शतपवाश च ववप्राङ्गी जननी
जना । कटुका वपत्तज्वत्तक्ता कटुः शीतास्त्रदािगजत् ।
बलासािोचकान् िग्तत ववषमज्विनामशनी ॥ ३८ ॥^[21]

Kaiyyadev Nighantu**Patol**

पटोलः कटुकस्तक्तः सिोषाः कफवपत्तनुत् । कण्डूदाितृषा
कोठकुष्ठिक्तज्विन् जयेत् ॥ ५६४ ॥ फलं तस्य कटु स्वादु
पाके ततक्तं िसे लघु । मलानुलोमनं वृष्यं हृद्यं
दीपनपाचनम् ॥ ५६५ ॥ म्स्नधोष्णं िोचनं िग्तत
दोषश्वासज्जिमीन् । पटोलपत्रं वपत्तघ्नं वल्ली चास्य कफापि ॥
फलं त्रत्रदोषशमनं मूलं तस्य वविचनम् ॥ ५६६ ॥
मूलं सिं वातििं पलाशनालं जिघ्नं तु फलं पटोल्याः ।
ततक्तं त्रत्रदोषज्विमेिकुष्ठका सकृमिघ्िं रुचचकृत्सपटोलम् ॥
५६७ ॥^[22]

Sariva

सारिवा मधुिा ततक्ता सुग्मनथा शुक्रला हिमा । गवी
ज्वाततसािामदोषत्रयववषापि । ६६५ ॥
अग्रनसादारुचचश्वासकासास्त्रप्रदिन् जयेत् ॥^[23]

Musta

मुस्तोऽम्भोदो घनं मुस्तं गाङ्गेयी कुरुववतदुकः । भद्रमुस्तो
वाििादः वपठि वपण्डमुस्तकम् ॥ १३५७ ॥ पूणशकोष्ठो
भद्रिसो प्राच्यो िाजकसेरुकः ।

मुस्तं ततक्तं हिमं ग्राहि दीपनं पाचनं कटु ॥ १३५८ ॥
कषायकफवपत्तास्रतृज्जिवा रुचचजन्तुजजत् ॥^[24]

Patha

पाठा तु कटुका तीक्ष्णा लघुरुष्णा त्रत्रदोषि ॥ ६७८ ॥
कुष्ठज्विच्छहदशदािाती सािहदूरुजः ।

िििेत्सगुल्म कण्डू ववषश्वासत्रणशूलगिकृिीिि ॥ ६७९ ॥
॥^[25]

Kutaki

कट्टी ततक्ता मत्स्यवपत्ता मत्स्यववतना द्ववजाचगका ॥ ११२१ ॥
कुष्ठभेदा काण्डरुिा चक्राङ्गी जननी कटुः ।

कटुका मत्स्यशकला िोहिणी शकुलादनी ॥ ११२२ ॥
अशोकिोहिणी ततक्तोहिणी कटुिोहिणी ।

कटुका शीतला ततक्ता कटुपाकिसा लघुः ॥ ११२३ ॥ भेदनी
दीपनी रूक्षा कफवपत्तज्जिवापि । प्रमेिक्षासकासाशशः
दािकुष्ठकृिीिि जयेत् ॥ ११२४ ॥^[26]

Review on Kushtha vyadhi• **Nidankarak sapta-dravyani**

1. Twak
2. Mamsa
3. Shonit
4. Lasika
5. Vata
6. Pitta
7. Kapha

• **Classification of kushtha**

1. Mahakushtha
2. Kshudrakushth

Mahakushtha	Charak samhita	Sushrut samhita	Ashtang hriday
1.	Kapal	Kapal	Kapal
2.	Udumber	Udumber	Udumber
3.	Mandal	Arun	Mandal
4.	Rushyajivha	Rushyajivha	Rushyajivha
5.	Pundarik	Pundarik	Pundarik
6.	Sidhma	Dadru	Dadru
7.	Kakanak	Kakanak	Kakanak

Pitta dosha predominance and rakt dushti is observed in
udumber kushtha

• **Krimi Types**

1. Abhyantar
2. Bahya

Abyantar krimi types

- 1) Kapha
- 2) Raktaj

2) Purishaj

- Antrad
- Udaraveshta
- Hridayad
- Mahakuha
- Kuru
- Darbhakusum
- Keshad
- Lomvidhwans
- Lomdvipa

- *Udumber*
- *Souras*
- *Mata*
- *Udumber krimi*- They found in *granthi* looking like *udumber phal*. Their proliferation occurs within the *granthi*.
- *Souras* – This type found around *kandara* i.e. cartilage. They feed on cartilage and damage their structure.
- *Mata*- This type lays eggs within affected areas and spread along the surrounding parts.

(Jantumata)

Kushtha samprapti

Mode of action of *raktapachak*

1. *Deepan* – Pacifies *rakta dhatwagni* due to *tikta rasa, ushna veerya*
2. *Panchan*- *raktadhatugat saamata pachan* by *katu, tikta rasa* and *ushna veerya*
3. *Shaman*- pitta shaman by *madhur, tikta rasa sheeta veerya (rakta-pitta ashrayashrayi bhav)*
4. *Krimighna karya*- Due to *teja, vaayu, aakash mahabhootadhikya*
5. *Kushthaghna*- Due to *vikrut kledopashoshan*
6. *Rasayan* – Due to *tikta* and *madhur rasa*

DISCUSSION

Raktapachak yoga has predominance of *aakasha* and *vayu mahabhoot*. Whereas *jala* and *pruthvi mahabhoot* are the key factors in *krimi* and *kushtha vyadhi*. Combination of *raktapachak yoga* has properties like *krimighna* and *kushthaghna* due to *aakash* and *vayu mahabhoot*. As name defines this combination already have tendency to act on *rakta dhatu*. Hence, *raktapachak* yoga pacifies *rakta dhatwagni* and results in *krimighna* and *kushthaghna* action.

CONCLUSION

This review on drugs in *Raktapachak* yoga implies *krimighna* and *kushthaghna* properties of this combination. Hence this combination can be implemented in *raktadhatu dushti, raktaj krimi, kushtha vyadhi*.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, charak samhita with hindi commentary chapter 3 chikitsa sthan citation 200 Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 186.
2. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 14 citation 42-56 chikitsa sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 534-535.
3. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 14 citation 51-52 chikitsa sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 535.
4. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 1 citation 7 sutra sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 8.
5. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 12 citation 1 nidan sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 512.
6. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 11 citation 27 chikitsa sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 165.
7. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Ashtang hriday with hindi commentary chapter 20 citation 34 chikitsa sthan Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 802.
8. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, charak samhita with hindi commentary chapter 7 chikitsa sthan citation 9-10 Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 301.
9. Priyavat Sharma Vaidya Vijay Shankar Kale Charak samhita with marathi commentary chapter 1 sutrasthan citation 44 Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 14.
10. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi charak samhita with hindi commentary chapter 15 Chikitsasthan citation 16 Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 553.
11. Priyavat Sharma Vaidya Vijay Shankar Kale Charak samhita with marathi commentary chapter 7 vimansthan citation 14 Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 606.
12. Padmashree Prof. Krishna Chandra chunekar Dr. Gangasahay Pandey Bhavprakash nighantu, Shaakvarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 672.
13. Padmashree Prof. Krishn Chandra chunekar Dr.

- Gangasahay Pandey Bhavprakash nighantu, guduchyadivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 411.
14. Padmashree Prof. Krishn Chandra chunekar Dr. Gangasahay Pandey Bhavprakash nighantu, Karpooradivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 232.
 15. Padmashree Prof. Krishna Chandra chunekar Dr. Gangasahay Pandey Bhavprakash nighantu, guduchyadivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 381.
 16. Padmashree Prof. Krishna Chandra chunekar Dr. Gangasahay Pandey Bhavprakash nighantu, haritakyadivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 67.
 17. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Dhanvantari nighantu guduchyadi varg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 25
 18. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Dhanvantari nighantu guduchyadi varg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 46.
 19. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Dhanvantari nighantu guduchyadi varg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 23.
 20. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Dhanvantari nighantu guduchyadi varg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 28.
 21. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Dhanvantari nighantu guduchyadi varg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 23.
 22. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Kaiyyadev nighantu Aushadhivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 103
 23. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Kaiyyadev nighantu Aushadhivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 184.
 24. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Kaiyyadev nighantu Aushadhivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 252.
 25. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Kaiyyadev nighantu Aushadhivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 125.
 26. Acharya Priyavat Sharma Kaiyyadev nighantu Aushadhivarg, Chaukhambha prakashan, Varanasi, page no. 207-208.